

FUEL PUMP PRICE MOVEMENT, ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The focus of this paper was on the effects of petroleum price changes on economic growth and development in Nigeria in the period 1980-2025. The specific objectives of the study were to examine the effects of PMS Price increase on inflation, unemployment and GDP. GDP and unemployment were the proxies for economic growth and economic development respectively. The data for the study were pooled from various sources such as National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), CBN Annual Reports and Statistics, economics texts, journals and World Bank data. To estimate the model, the researcher employed Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag models (ARDL) as inferential statistical tool of analysis. With unemployment as a dependent variable the result of the analysis indicated that unemployment in the previous period had significant positive effect on the current level of unemployment in Nigeria. Petrol price increase had significant positive impact on inflation rate in Nigeria. With GDP as a dependent variable and petroleum price and inflation as explanatory variables, the results indicated that Petroleum Pump Price increase had significant negative effect on real GDP in Nigeria. Inflation rate had significant negative effect on real GDP in Nigeria. Implications of the findings: the results from the findings indicated that changes in the price of PMS introduced significant shock to Nigerian economy in terms of increased rise in the costs of business resulting cost push inflation which caused investment dwindle to worsen the level of unemployment. This scenario implied that fiscal policy was not very effective at this time to contain the level of inflation induced by changes in the price of PMS.*

Keywords: *Fuel Pump Price, Economic Growth and Development.*

1.0 Introduction and Background

Fuel subsidy withdrawal has been a long debated policy since the early 1970s. For instance, the withdrawal of fuel subsidy began in 1973 with General Yakubu Gowon military administration. At this time, the price of PMS was raised from 0.06Naira to 0.0845Naira. The major partial attempts of fuel subsidy withdrawal were in the 2000s and the full removal was in May 2023 by president Bola Tinubu, marking the end of decades of state funded subsidies that kept pump price artificially low. Various reasons were adduced for the removal of fuel subsidy in Nigeria, among which was that the beneficiaries of fuel subsidy were mainly the wealthy; hence, its withdrawal was for broader economic reforms and sustainable growth. Another reason was that billions of naira was defrauded by

politicians under fuel subsidy, amounting to 2-3% of the GDP annually that introduced fiscal strains.

More importantly, Fuel crisis from subsidy regime was the cause of black market price escalation, transportation and logistics paralysis, inflationary pressures and power shortages especially where generators substitute grid electricity. Again fuel subsidies encouraged corruption, inefficiency, fuel import dependency, and worsening foreign exchange pressure (Akinbodo, 2022; Akinola, 2021; Anosike, 2024; Bibi-Farouk, 2020; Gidigwi&Bello2020). Hence its withdrawal was to free subsidies fund amounting to \$10billion spent annually on fuel subsidy for economic diversification, agriculture and health as well as to boost long term GDP by 1-3% through private investment in refineries to reduce import reliance averaging 5% (SERAP, 2025; Chukwuemeka, 2013). That removal the removal of fuel subsidy would mitigate fuel scarcity, long queues at the fuel stations.

When Murtala Mohammed took over the governance after military coup, the price of PMS was raised from 0.0845Naira to 0.09Naira in 1976. After the bloody coup that assassinated General Mutala Mohammed, General Olusegun Obasanjo took over the governance in October 1st 1978. This administration raised the price of PMS from 0.09Naira to 0.153Naira. By 1979 General Olusegun Obasanjo handed over to a civilian president Alhaji Shehu Shagari. In April 20th 1979, this administration raised the price of PMS from 0.153N to 0.20Naira. After General Ibrahim Babangida took over governance from Shehu Shagari through military coup, on the 31st of March 1986, he raised the price of PMS from 0.02Naira to 0.395N, then to 0.42Naira on April 10th 1988. The same administration raised the price of petrol to 0.60Naira on the 19th December 1989, again to 0.70Naira on the 6th March 1991, which lasted until August 1993, when General Ibrahim Babangida stepped aside as military president (CBN Annual, Report and account, 2021; CBN Bulletin, 1982; Ayodele, 1982). By November 8 1993, Nigeria's transition president - Ernest Shonekan who took over governance from General Ibrahim Babangida raised the price of PMS from 0.70Naira to N5.00. This astronomical rise in the price of PMS provoked mass protest that ushered in another military coup by General Sani Abacha who reduced the price of PMS from N5.00 to N3.25 on the 22nd of November 1993. Then on the 2nd of October 1994, this administration raised the price of PMS from N3.25 to N15.00, another jump in the price of PMS in Nigeria. After a wide spread protest, the price of PMS was reduced to N11.00 on the 4th of October 1994. This was the price of PMS till 8th June 1988 General Abacha passed on. Then on the 20th of December, the price of PMS was raised from N11.00 to N25.00 under General Abdul-Salami Abubakar. After a sustained protest, it was reduced to N20.00 on the 6th of January 1999(Amogo, 2014; SERAP, 2025; Olomola &Adejumo, 2016; Akindele, 2014). The issue of fuel subsidy was not an issue until the second return of General Obasanjo to power in 1999.

The return of General Olusegun Obasanjo, this time as a civilian president, introduced fuel subsidy as the bedrock of economic policy in Nigeria. On the 1st of June 2000, this administration raised the price of PMS from N20.00 to N30.00. This shift in the price of pms attracted mass protest which

forced the government to reduce the price to N15.00. On the 13th of June 2000, the government raised it to N22.00. In January 2002, the price of PMS was raised to N26.00 and was shifted again to N42.00 on June 2003. The same regime increased the price of PMS to N50.00 on the 29th of May 2004, then to N65.00 on 25th August 2004, and N75.00 on 27th May 2007.

Musa Yaradua took over governance in 2007; he reduced the price of PMS to N65.00. When he died, GoodLuck Jonathan took over governance he continued with the gradual withdrawal of fuel subsidy. GoodLuck administration raised the price of PMS from N65.00 N141.00 on the 1st January, 2012; but later reduced it to N97.00 after violent protest .By 2015; Buhari's government raised the price of PMS to N145.00. This regime maintained this price till 2017 when it was raised to N150. Then considering the hardship in the country behind fuel increase, Musa Yaradua's regime reduced the price of PMS to N145.00 in 2018. By 2020 due to global oil shock, the price of PMS was raised to N160. The due to COVID 19 pandemic, in 2021, the price of PMS was raised to N170, then to N195 in 2022. It was President Tinubu's administration that raised the price of PMS N626 in 2023, N700 in 2024 and N900 in 2025 marking complete withdrawal of subsidy in Nigeria (NNPC 2025; AJdua&Ojima 2014; Dike, 2018; Okafor, 2018). Therefore the issues of fuel pump price increase are the aftermath of fuel subsidy withdrawal.

The post Fuel price increase of 2023 caused food and transport costs to go up to the range of 20-30%, limiting access to services and widening the urban –rural divides, undermining HDI gains such as education and health. Sharp pump price hikes from N185 to over N600 per litre initially fuelled inflation, transport costs and economic hardship for many Nigerians and challenges in economic growth and development (Adagunodo, 2022). It foresters structural issues such as corruption and weak safety nets giving rise to social unrest and stalled poverty reduction, with unemployment rising amid cost of living crisis. According to Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) (2025), Nigerian governors and the FCT could not account for the over N14TN realized from fuel pump price changes since 2023. Surges in prices due to changes in pump price changes exacerbate poverty and inequality via living costs. Over the years Nigerian government has failed to target appropriately palliatives for fuel price increases which resulted in hindering equitable development more than economic growth (Igwe& Chukwuemeka, 2015; Baghebo&Atima, 2023). Since the 1980s the relationship between PMS Price changes and inflation and growth has received much theoretical attention without sufficient proof in Nigeria. Hence this paper is an attempt to bridge this gap. Furthermore, this piece of study, might serve as a reference document for economics researchers. The situation in Nigeria over fuel price changes has continued to raise some relevant questions over economic growth and development. The following questions have been raised: What is the effect of Petroleum Pump Price on real GDP in Nigeria; what is the effect of inflation on real GDP in Nigeria; what is the effect of Petroleum Pump Price of employment level in Nigeria? Hence, the following are research Objectives: To examine the effect of petroleum pump price increase on the GDP growth in Nigeria; To examine the effect of inflation on real GDP in Nigeria; To examine the effect of petroleum

pump price employment level in Nigeria. The rest of the paper was structured as follows: section 2 is the review of relevant literature; section 3 is theoretical framework and methodology; section 4 is presentation and analysis of result; section 5 is summary of findings, conclusion and implications of the findings.

2.0 Review of the Relevant Literature

2.1. Conceptual Issues

FUEL: Fuel is a substance or material that undergoes combustion/ a chemical reaction to release energy for powering engines or to generate heat or to drive machinery. Common examples of fuel include fossil fuels such as gasoline (petrol, diesel, and natural gas, and coal, renewable energy like such as bio-fuels, hydrogen or electricity in modern contexts. Pump Price implies the retail price that consumers pay at the filling stations per liters.

Fuel Pump Price Increase: is a government policy to increase the retail prices of petroleum products (petrol, diesel and kerosene). In Nigeria the idea of increasing the fuel price is to cover the difference between imports or production costs and what the consumer pay at the pump which is often funded through oil revenues to make fuel more affordable and control inflation. Fuel price increase was introduced in Nigeria in the post-independence era which was intensified during the 1970s oil boom. Such increase was aimed at supporting agriculture, transport and manufacturing to reduce operational costs which was criticized as efforts to encourage smuggling, corruption etc. Removal of fuel subsidy refers to government decision to eliminate the financial supports or price controls on petroleum products in order to allow market forces to determine their prices. Fuel price increase was aimed at freeing fund estimated at \$10billion annually in the name of subsidy by government that could fund infrastructure, health, education and encourage private investment in fuel refining and reduce corruption in subsidy claims.

Fuel Crisis: Fuel crisis is the recurring shortages of fuel relative to demand resulting to demand pressures that shift prices of fuel upward. Fuel crisis in Nigeria is as a result of structural dependency, weak local refining, foreign exchange volatility that affects import costs, policy inconsistency, as in subsidy regimes and deregulation changes. Fuel crisis due to short supply relative demand resulting in scarcity of fuel, long queues, price hikes, and economic disruptions were blamed at existence of fuel subsidy.

Economic Growth

This refers to increase in country's production of goods and services over time which is typically measured by the rise in the real GDP. Economic growth signals an expanding economy that is driven by investment, technology, labor productivity and trade. Increased pump price of fuel results in increased household expenditure and reduced purchasing power (microeconomic impact). It results in dwindling GDP growth rate, inflationary spikes, and industrial under performance (macroeconomic impacts). In this paper the proxy for economic growth is the real GDP.

Economic Development

Economic development is the broader process of improving the overall quality of life and wellbeing in a society through sustainable increases in income, productivity and structural changes. Economic development emphasizes equitable distribution, poverty reduction, better education, healthcare, infrastructure and environmental protection often measured by indices such as HDI. For instance, persistent issues such as unemployment at over 20% and inequality limit fuller progress, highlighting the need for inclusive policies. There are social/political implications involved in fuel increases, such as public frustration, protests, and reputational damage for government. All these are involved with the welfare of the people and overall economic development. And economic development is sustained improvement in the quality of life and well-being of the people through economic growth, social transformation, and institutional strengthening. For the interest of this economic development implies employment generation unemployment level, income distribution, productivity and personal income (Akubote, 2021; Olusegun, 2021; Olomola, 2021). Studies have shown that petroleum prices often have negative long run impact the GDP, with diesel and kerosene hikes correlating to 0.5-2% GDP drags in short term shocks. On the growth side, elevated prices may curb fiscal deficits (Sanusi, 2023). The proxy for economic development is unemployment.

2.2 Theories of Growing Size of Government/Market Economy

These theories explain perfectly well why the public sector has expanded over the years in Nigeria. Keynes(1936) counter cyclical theory explained further why inability to control expenditures and budget deficits contributed to expanding government size in Nigeria; while Pommerehne & Schneider(1978) fiscal illusion theory provide explanation why the public utility users in Nigeria cannot fully discount and capitalize future tax burden from current public debt which results in growing size of government. Note rising public debt service payments, implies growing size of government as well as rising relative of government, and dwindling growth. Huge expenditures of government without output growth have always resulted in monetary growth and inflation. In the name of deregulation, the issues of public debts, high rates of inflation and unemployment, capacity underutilization, rising external dependence and poverty have continued to worsen. The linkages between pump price increase, economic growth and development draw from the neoclassical, Keynesian, and resource base theories, emphasizing energy as a key input in production and consumption. In the neoclassical context, higher pump prices act as a supply shock, raising the production costs for energy-dependent sectors such transport and manufacturing thereby shifting the aggregate supply curves leftward reducing output and GDP growth, introducing cost push inflation. Hence, energy price hikes propagate through supply channels, curbing investment and productivity. Keynesian theory highlights demand side effects. In line with this proposition elevated prices erode disposable income, and consumer confidence, leading to reduced spending on nonessential goods, which dampens aggregate demands and slows down economic growth. In oil economies like that of Nigeria, pump price increase amplifies fiscal strain, through higher import bills which would

potentially crowd out public investment in infrastructures and social services. In line with endogenous growth theory, sustained high prices hinder human capital accumulation and innovation by increasing living costs, exacerbating inequality and poverty. Unless offset by diversification as per Dutch disease models where energy volatility traps economies in resource dependence (Omorkeji, 2014; Gujarati, Porter&Gunasekar2012).

2.3 Empirical Literature

Twinsa(2017) examined the effect of subsidy removal on Nigeria's economy in the period 2000-2016. The following variables were examined: real GDP, CPI, and the price of PMS. Ordinary Least squares (OLS) technique was employed to test the hypothesis. The result of the study indicated that fuel subsidy removal had negative effect on real growth.

Olomola& Adejumo(2016) examined the effect of oil price shock on output, inflation, real exchange rate and money supply in the period 1970-2003. The author employed VAR technique. The result of the study indicated that oil price shock had no significant on output and inflation but had significant positive effect on exchange rate movement.

Olusegun(2018) examined the effect of oil price shock on macroeconomic performance in Nigeria. Variables such as real GDP, CPI, real oil revenue, real money supply, real government expenditures, capital expenditures and real oil price were tested. VAR technique was employed by the author. The result of the study indicated that movement in oil price had significant negative effect on real GDP and capital expenditure.

Aliyu (2019) examined the effect of oil shock, real exchange volatility on real growth in the period 1986-2007. Vector Error Correction Model was employed by the author to estimate the model. The results of the analysis indicated that oil shock had significant positive effect on exchange rate and output.

Onwuka,Chiekezie & Igweze(2018) examine the effect of fuel prices on economic growth in Nigeria. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique was employed to test the hypotheses. The result of the analysis indicated that fuel price increase had significant negative effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ajudua & Ojima(2016) examined the effect of oil price increase on economic growth in Nigeria. VAR technique was employed by the author to test the hypothesis. The result of the analysis indicated that oil price had negative effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Okafor(2018) examined movement in petroleum pump price and standard of living in Nigeria in the period 1980- 2017. The following variables were tested: capital income, Inflation and real GDP. To test the hypothesis, the author employed regression method. The result indicated that pump price oil movement had significant negative effect on capital income and inflation.

3.0 Theoretical Framework and Methodology

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The linkages between pump price increase, economic growth and development draw from the neoclassical, Keynesian, and resource base theories, emphasizing energy as a key input in production and consumption. In the neoclassical context, higher pump prices act as a supply shock, raising the production costs for energy-dependent sectors such transport and manufacturing thereby shifting the aggregate supply curves leftward reducing output and GDP growth ,introducing cost push inflation .Hence, energy price hikes propagates through supply channels ,curbing investment and productivity. Keynesian theory highlights demand side effects. In line with this proposition elevated prices erode disposable income, and consumer confidence, leading to reduced spending on nonessential goods, which dampens aggregate demands and slows down economic growth. In oil economies like that of Nigeria, pump price increase amplifies fiscal strain, through higher import bills which would potentially crowd out public investment in infrastructures and social services. In line with endogenous growth theory, sustained high prices hinder human capital accumulation and innovation by increasing living costs, exacerbating inequality and poverty. Unless offset by diversification as per Dutch disease models where energy volatility traps economies in resource dependence (Omorkeji, 2014; Gujarati, Porter&Gunasekar2012).

Fuel price has inverse relationship with economic growth and development in Nigeria. And that higher pump prices typically from fuel subsidy removals or market liberalization increase production and transport costs, raise inflation, reduce consumer spending, squeeze manufacturing output, and slows down economic growth. Therefore the objectives of this paper are to determine empirically whether there is excessive public sector by examining the relationship between the relative size of government and GDP and to determine the effect of inflation on growth in Nigeria.

Model Specification

$$GDP=F(PPP, INFL)..... (3.1)$$

GDP is gross domestic product; ppp is petroleum pump price

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PPP + \beta_2 INFL (3.2)$$

β_0 Is a constant ; β_1 is the coefficient of petroleum pump price; β_2 is the coefficient of inflation.

PPP>0; INFL>0

$$UNEMP=F(PPP, INFL)..... (3.3)$$

UNEMP =unemployment;

INFL<0; PPP<0

$$UNEMP=\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 (3.4)$$

α_0 Is the intercept; α_1 is the coefficient of pump price; α_2 is the coefficient of inflation

3.2 Methodology

Methodology for this paper is purely econometrics involving statement of theory, specification of model, obtaining of data, estimation of empirical model, hypothesis testing and forecasting. Secondary data such as price of petrol real GDP, unemployment rate ,and inflation rate from 1980 to

2025 from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), CBN Annual Reports and Accounts, World Bank and various sources were used for the study . To estimate equation 3.2 Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method was employed.

4.1. Presentation and Analysis of Results

Table 4.1: ARDL Results

Dependent Variable: Unemployment

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Probability
UNEMPLOYMENT	0.572062	0.1588100	3.60215300	0.0022
PPP	0.066647	0.3189800	2.08935400	0.0500
INFL	-1.031244	1.074616	-0.9959639	0.3518
INFL(-1)	-0.696797	1.091573	-0.6383420	0.2521
INFL(-2)	-1.201925	1.013900	-1.1854470	0.2023
INFL(-3)	-1.373017	1.035218	1.32630700	0.2023
C	60.66051	26.78371	2.26482800	0.0369

Source: Researcher's computation

R-Squared	0.69938	Mean dependent var	35.04375
Adj.R-Squared	0.593290	SD dependent var	23.61088
S.E Regression	15.05756	Akaike Infor criter	8.500131
Sum Squared Resid	3854.414	Schwarz Criter	8.843730
LogLikelihood	-95.00157	Hannan Qin Criter	8.591288
F-Statistic	6.591885	Durbin Watson stat	2.371022
Prob(F-Stat)	0.0000976		

Table 4.2: ARDL Test Result

Dependent variable: GDP

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-statistic	Probability
GDP(-1)	0.078424	0.252836	0.310179	0.7622
DP(-2)	0.268872	0.200967	1.337888	0.2079
PPP	414518.7	244601.9	-1.694667	0.0082
PPP(-1)	-214010.3	305988.2	-0.699407	0.4988
PPP(-2)	-11950.22	291460.0	-0.041001	0.9680
PPP(-3)	1233689	1340433	0.920366	0.3771
PPP(-4)	2315526	1532195	1.511247	0.1589
INFL	-550191.4	5931950	-0.092751	0.0078
INFL(-1)	4671714	6079346	0.768457	0.4584
INFL(-2)	15836919	5652725	2.801643	0.0172
INFL(-3)	6425264	5439839	1.181150	0.2625

C	-4.44E+08	1.45E+08	-3.072454	0.0106
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Source: Searcher's Computation

R-Squared 0.936882	Mean dependent var 1.67+E08
Adj R-Squared 0.873763	S.D dependent var 1.941E08
S.E of regression 68896212	Akaika infor critarion 39.23998
Sum Squared Resid 5.22E+16	Schwarz criterion 3983241
Log Likelihood -439.2598	Hannan-Quinn criterion 39.38897
F-statistic 1484324	Durbin-Watson statistic 2.127115
Prob(F-statistic) 0.000047	

Table 4.1, presents the results of the relationship between PPP and unemployment level which serves as the relevant proxy for development in this study. The results of the ARDL test results indicate that the effect of PPP movement on unemployment in the first period (-1) had significant negative effect on employment rate at less than 5% level of significance. For every 1% increase in unemployment level, unemployment in the first period (-1) contributed 0.6%. PPP movement had significant positive effect on employment and unemployment in the reviewed period. For every 1% increase in unemployment level, PPP contributed 0.07%. Inflation had no significant effect at 5% level of significance. The constant was statistically significant at less than 5% level of significance. The model has goodness of fit. For instance, the R Squared could explain 70% of the relationship between the independent and explanatory variables. Then with the probability statistic of 0.000976, the model was free from multi co linearity. The model was free from autocorrelation with the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.37.

Table 4.2 presents the relationship between GDP and PPP. In determining the effect of petroleum pump price increase on the GDP, the result indicated that lag in the first (-1) and second (-2) periods had no significant effect on GDP growth in Nigeria in the period 1999-2025. Pump price movement (PPP) had significant negative effect on GDP in the reviewed period .For every 1% increase in GDP PPP movement had 414518.7% depressing effect on the GDP in the period 1999-2025.This implies that rise in the cost of business induced by pump price increase, depressed investment ,productivity and created unemployment in the period . It also implies that pump price increase depressed economic development in the period .PPP in the first (-1) second (-2), third (-3) forth (-4) had no significant effect on GDP growth in Nigeria the reviewed period. Inflation had significant negative effect on the GDP at less than 5% level of significance in the reviewed period in Nigeria. For every 1% increase in GDP or productivity, inflation depressed the GDP by 5500191%. Inflation in the second period (-2) had significant negative effect on the GDP at less than 5% level of significance. This implies that cost push inflation at this period negated investment. The strength of the overall model shows that the R-Squared was 0.94 implying that the model could explain94% of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The F-statistic of 0.000045 probabilities indicated that that the F-statistic was significant at less than 5% level of significance, implying that

there was no case of multi-co linearity. In testing for autocorrelation, the Durbin –Watson statistic of 2.13, indicating that there was no case of autocorrelation.

5.1 Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1.1 Summary of Findings

From empirical findings, petroleum pump price increase in Nigeria induced rise in the costs of transportation, food and services, resulting in the rising cost of business –cost push inflation. Cost push inflation during this period depressed investment, worsened the level of unemployment and economic growth. Meanwhile, beginning from the 1980s, Nigerian economy had witnessed worsening unemployment ;and from empirical findings, arrears of worsened unemployment level or unemployment level in the previous periods contributed significantly to the current level of unemployment in Nigeria in the reviewed period.

Conclusion

The empirical findings indicated that pump price movement in the reviewed period was inflationary, and resulted in poor investment, growth and frustration of development process. Fuel pump price increase worsened economic growth and economic development with the real GDP and unemployment level as relevant proxies respectively. More importantly, fuel price increase evidenced by the outcome of the present study, has remained the major trigger of inflationary pressure and poverty in Nigeria.

Implications /Recommendations

Implications of the findings: the results from the findings indicated that changes in the price of PMS introduced significant shock to Nigerian economy in terms of increased rise in the costs of business resulting cost push inflation that caused investment dwindle to worsen the level of unemployment. This scenario implied that fiscal policy was not very effective at this time to contain the level of inflation induced by changes in the price of PMS. Pump price induced inflation as in the case of Nigeria can be mitigated through a mixed gradual reforms, fiscal reallocations and structural interventions aimed at cushioning short term shocks, while fostering long term stability through the following: Phased, subsidy removal: implement step by step increases in pump prices to avoid abrupt shocks, allowing time for economic adjustments and reducing immediate inflationary pressure from cost push effects. Targeted cash transfer and safety nets provide direct payment or vouchers to vulnerable group especially revival and low income households to offset rising living cost and maintain purchasing power amid inflation spikes. Supply side reforms: Invest in infrastructure (agriculture, transport) and productivity enhancement to ease bottlenecks, stabilize food prices and promote completion e.g. agricultural tech to counter food inflation from transport hikes. Monetary and fiscal tightening: Use inflation- targeting frameworks transparent budgeting and reduced spending to anchor expectations and build credibility while enhancing public transport to lower fuel demands. Anti-corruption efforts and political will are crucial in actualizing all this recommendations.

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